

Justified Cybersecurity Threat and Risk Assessment

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Abstract—Cybersecurity risk and threat assessment is nowadays performed starting from a number of incomplete and unjustified cybersecurity threats. We propose a methodology that, starting from a justified set of cybersecurity properties, induces all possible threats to those properties. Once the threats are identified, the risks calculation can be justified, providing quantitative and qualitative results that do not merely rely on the expertise of the person performing the assessment.

Index Terms—cybersecurity, threat assessment, risk assessment

1. Introduction

Context and Motivation. Cybersecurity Risk Assessment (CRA from now on), is the process where cyber-risks are identified, prioritized, and mitigated based on an analysis of potential cyber-threats¹. Suppose one wants to perform a CRA of a physical cable to estimate its cybersecurity risks and prioritize investments on risk mitigations. One first defines a list of *known* threats (induced from previous incidents related to our use case), such as having a weakly shielded cable. One then determines the related vulnerabilities² as, for example, jamming the cable communication, and estimate the likelihood and impact of such a vulnerability. Expertise is leveraged to evaluate the vulnerability considering some, non-standard, measures such as “physical accessibility of the cable to a threat actor”; reaching conclusions such as: if the cable is installed in a restricted area, it is *less likely* to be attacked than if the cable were installed into a public office. One can even consider the accessibility of the cable to different *threat actors* [30]. For example, considering an *external* threat actor (e.g., as a malicious fake-customer) or an *insider* threat; determining that the vulnerability considered is less likely in the case of an external attacker *unless* the cable is in use at, e.g., the reception desk (being exposed to customers and, in turn, to external threats). All these considerations *induce from experience* and are used to evaluate risks quantitatively or qualitatively. Expertise, not science, becomes

1. When the attribute cyber- is omitted from risk and threats, in this paper we only consider cybersecurity threats and risks.

2. A vulnerability, see [36] for the CVE database of vulnerabilities, is an implementation of the abstract weakness or threats; the CWE database in [37] is a collection of such weaknesses.

the key factor for executing a CRA. However, thousands of new vulnerabilities are publicly reported every month (e.g., 28961 vulnerabilities have been collected by the CVE program in 2023 [38]), making the results of CRAs often doubted even by those experts who performed the assessment. A CRA *should* give an overview of the cybersecurity posture of a company, system, or technology but, with the lack of a common scientific ground, CRA ends up being expensive, doubtful, and sometimes so imprecise that the investments in risk reduction are wrongly prioritized.

Research Challenge and Contribution. The main challenge for the current approaches to CRA (see Threat-Modeler [16], IRAM2 [1]) is related to the problem of induction. From a finite number of empirical observations we cannot formulate a general, scientific solution to any problem (unless violating Popper’s demarcation principle [28]). Similarly, from a finite number of insecurities (e.g., vulnerabilities or weaknesses from the NIST NVD database [26]) we cannot predict the cybersecurity or insecurity of a business, system, or technology. We address this challenge relating fundamental properties of information theory to a structure of cybersecurity properties which are then used to *deduce* the threats and calculate their risk. Summarizing, our contributions are:

- 1) We design a CRA process in BPMN [27], from a review of the state of the art (in Appendix B), discussing the challenges of each subprocess.
- 2) We determine a structure of cybersecurity properties based on information theory (e.g. entropy, information).
- 3) We propose a framework for the threat and risk assessment which we showcase to an ad-hoc use case.

2. Challenges in Cyber-Risk Assessment

CRA is a process that, given a system (model), determines a *quantitative or qualitative* estimation of the cybersecurity risk posed by the potential cyber-insecurities of the system. As depicted in Figure 1³, the CRA process is usually divided into two major consecutive parts that deal with the **assessment of the threats** and with the **management of the risk** respectively. This CRA process, along with the details

3. The diagram follows the BPMN (Business Process Model and Notation) language with a slight abuse of notation for the names of the pools.

Figure 1: High-level Diagram of a Cybersecurity Risk Assessment Process

Figure 2: Subprocess “Define system model”

Figure 3: Subprocess “Determine Threat Scenarios”

in this section, are the result of an extensive review of the state of the art, summarized in Appendix B.

2.1. System Model

The CRA process starts with the definition of a **model of the system**; where “system” is a generic term that, depending on the field of application, may have different meanings, e.g. referring to one or more software or hardware components (or an aggregation of them as in cyber-physical systems). For the sake of simplicity, let us consider a **generic cable as a system** (an abstraction of, e.g., an Ethernet cable). A model of a generic cable can be defined starting from the **requirement** that “the cable shall transfer data from one of its ends to the other”. This requirement can be **modeled as an equality** relation between the input and output data. Therefore, we detail (see Figure 2) the subprocess “Define system model” with two tasks: *requirements definition* and *requirement formalization*. An extensive review of the modeling languages and processes is out of the scope of this paper but, for the purpose of this investigation, **we consider a formal model to be a mathematical formula representing an interpretation of a requirement**. Furthermore, we assume a system to be a structure of one or more atomic⁴ subsystems; where a subsystem is atomic if defined by a *single* requirement which terms are ground truths. Hence, a formalization of a system into a system model can be considered a mathematical structure (e.g., a graph or a lattice) whose internal subsystems are each semantically defined by a single mathematical formula. One now faces a widely discussed problem:

4. Atomic, in this paper, is used to highlight the absence (or non-necessity) of inner or further (sub)definitions.

Q1 What are **cybersecurity requirements** and how do they differ from other requirements?

It is frightening that this question does not have a clear answer and that recent papers (such as [13, 14]) trace question back to 1986 where the author in [12] states that “[w]e need some clear, precise definitions of the cybersecurity concepts needed to express what is required of a secure system”, making it explicit that “[w]e need some ways of building systems to those requirements” and that “[o]ne of the things that is essential to proving that a system meets a requirement is abstraction”.

2.2. Threat Scenarios

The second subprocess, as depicted in Figure 3, is the one that generates the **threat scenarios** starting from a (formal) model of the system. Informally, a threat scenario is a *description of one or more events that impede or negatively impact the requirements (or the nominal behavior) of a system*. We highlight that a threat scenario is a general term that encompasses threats and their interpretation as vulnerabilities of the system. Considering our running example, the threat “weak shielding of the cable” may become the vulnerability: a malicious agent cuts the cable. We call threat scenarios the set of threats along with their vulnerabilities if the scenarios describe a situation in which a requirement does not hold; in our example, the requirements are impacted as the cable does not “transfer the data”.

While this informal definition is often believed to suffice in practice, as soon as one tries to structure this subprocess he must tackle questions which seem impossible to answer.

Q2 How can all the (important) threats and threat scenarios be identified? Or, if all the threats cannot be qualitatively listed, what is the magnitude of the space of all the threats?

Figure 4: Subprocess “Calculate Likelihood of Threat Scenarios”

TABLE 1: Likelihood scale example

Likelihood	Measures			
	Past threat exploitation		Offensive skills	
Low	Never	1	Ad-hoc tools	1
Medium	Once	2	Advanced tools	2
High	Multiple	3	Basic tools	3

Without answering to Q2, the CRA process may give a *false sense of security or insecurity* as it may leave out important threats (zero-days are hardly ever considered in CRA processes), or doesn’t correctly weight the threats with respect to all conceivable threats (or categories of threats). Great care should be taken in addressing this question since threats are correlated with the behaviors of a system and Q2 may easily become undecidable (Rice’s theorem [29]).

2.3. Likelihood of Threat Scenarios

The **likelihood** estimation is the *probability* that the exploitation of a threat scenario is realized within the lifetime of the system. It is, however, impossible (as of today) to define this “probability” as long as Q2 does not have an answer; one lacks the definition of the probability space. The result is that likelihood estimations are most often (if not always) related to beliefs or heuristics (e.g. by considering psychological aspects of the threat agent as the “gain” in realizing a threat) and not to scientific theories. A likelihood scale (see [22] for a detailed discussion on likelihood) is often defined as in Table 1, over a finite set of **measures**⁵. One may be tempted to investigate which measure should be used to calculate the likelihood, instead of answering to Q2. However, determining these measures is equivalent to defining a system of categories to describes a threat (scenario). Defining a concept in terms of categories is a problem studied since the dawn of philosophy and no definite answer is known [39]. Instead, **one needs a general mathematical interpretation of the concept “threat” that allows a categorization of possible threats**. Once the categorization is formalized, one may define a probability space and then the likelihood of that specific threat. In our running example, this equates to asking which is the probability that “cutting

5. A measure being a parameter which can be valued over a given mathematical structure.

the cable” is realized, and then asking which are *all* other threats that compose the probability space of threats over a cable. Given that the requirement is defined as an *equality* between the quantity and quality of data transferred by the cable, we can hypothesize that the threats are all classifiable considering the qualitative or quantitative variations of this *equality*. So, input data may be equal or different from the output data, otherwise one may say that the quantity of input data (e.g., the quantity of bits) is less than, or greater than the output. This example does not want to be complete or precise, but clear. It is here used to give an intuition of what is meant with the process described above and depicted in Figure 4. We can now summarize the whole section with the following question.

Q3 Which mathematical object (i.e., definition) should be used to determine the probability space of threat scenarios? Or which considerations should be taken into account when selecting a mathematical object to interpret threats and threat scenarios?

2.4. Impact of Threat Scenarios

The **impact** calculation quantitatively or qualitatively estimates the damage of the threats, vulnerabilities, or threat scenarios. An impact scale (similar to the likelihood scale in Table 1) is often defined over the CIA-Triad (Confidentiality, Integrity, Availability [34]). However, the impact calculation *requires* the definition of “what is of value” or of the **assets** related to the system under assessment. For example, in the descriptions of the impact measures in the CVSS v3 [5] there are sentences like: “Access to some *restricted information* is obtained [...]” (our italics) and one must define which are the “restricted information”. Our running example is a system considered in isolation, and any system in total isolation has no risk, not just because it cannot be accessed to but because it serves no purpose and any threat realized on that system would have *no asset* to impact. For the purpose of CRA, systems are considered along with the **business processes** they support, where a business process is not necessarily a process implemented by a company or related to trade, but a general process that is of interest to someone or something. The assets are then related to the business process (or processes) that requires the system under assessment. For example, our cable is the system while the relation of the cable to the business processes could be one of the following.

- The sales department that uses the cable to contact (via phone or email) the customers. Cutting the cable may impact on the sales department business processes.
- The cable is a famous piece of art exposed in a museum and cutting the cable would impact on the revenue of the museum or increase the cost of the insurance subscribed by the museum.

This definition of the assets is usually defined on a case-by-case basis assuming that there is no general definition of asset that applies to all the systems or business processes. This notion is central (as we show in the next step of the

Figure 5: Subprocess “Calculate Impact of Threat Scenarios”

Figure 6: Subprocess “Risk Estimation”

process) for the calculation of risk and a misinterpretation of it may result in a wrong estimation of risk.

Q4 Is there a general list/structure of assets or how can one determine the assets given a system? How can then impact be calculated over those assets?

The impact calculation subprocess is summarized in Figure 5 where the impact of threat scenarios is evaluated over the assets, business processes, and technologies.

2.5. Risk

The **estimation of the overall risk** (summarized in Figure 6) is usually obtained by multiplying the quantitative estimation of the likelihood $likelihood(t)$ with the estimation of the impact $impact(t)$ on each threat scenario t . This produces an ordered (high-to-low risk) list of threats scenarios. More precisely, given a list of n threat scenarios t_1, \dots, t_n we calculate $risk(t_i) = likelihood(t_i) \times impact(t_i)$ ⁶. Both likelihood and impact are usually calculated as the average over the multiple measures considered so the formula for the likelihood (and similarly for the impact) is $likelihood(t_i) = \frac{1}{m} \sum_{j=1}^m measure_j(t_i)$ where each j -th measure is a quantitative estimation.

Q5 What is the correct formula to calculate the risk? How can we define the proper formula for the risk calculation?

6. The use of multiplication is related to the widespread use of heat-maps or risk matrices where the risk is determined by the pair likelihood-impact, e.g. (2, 3) for a threat with medium likelihood and high impact.

Figure 7: Subprocess “Mitigation Strategy Definition”

Using the average (over the estimations of the measures for likelihood and impact) implies that either all the measures are of the same relevance (for the risk calculation), or that the relevance has been considered in the likelihood and impact scales (e.g., low relevance from 1 to 5, high above 5), but *how can one define this “relevance”*?

2.6. Mitigation Strategy

The objective of the **mitigation strategy**, as depicted in Figure 7, is to determine the **treatment actions** to mitigate all the threat scenarios which risk is unacceptable. We now consider only a quantitative approach but qualitative considerations are often considered at this step (e.g., to prioritize treatments that can be used to showcase cybersecurity concerns/skills to a company). A list of threat scenarios is down-selected by considering a *risk threshold* above which the risk cannot be accepted. For example, if “cutting the cable” has a risk of 9 and “tampering the cable” of 6, and we only have the budget or resources to mitigate one threat scenario, we can set the risk threshold to 7. Another approach would be to set the risk threshold based on the likelihood and impact scales, deciding a-priori which impact/likelihood are acceptable. However, final adjustments, related to external factors such as budget and timing often affect this second case too.

Once the list of unacceptable threat scenarios is defined, the mitigation subprocess continues by evaluating potential treatment options, identifying the definitive set of actions and re-calculating the risk over those treated threat scenarios. Mitigations are usually defined based on recommendations made by experts and, in general, are most often (if not always) based on past experience. Mitigations may only reduce the likelihood or impact of a threat scenario

TABLE 2: Relation between CRA process and challenges

Step	Q&A
System	Q1 - What are cybersecurity requirements?
Threat	Q2 - How can <i>all</i> the threats be identified?
Likelihood	Q3 - How can likelihood be formally defined?
Impact	Q4 - How can impact on the assets be calculated?
Risk	Q5 - How can the overall risk be calculated?
Mitigation	Q6 - How can risk threshold and mitigations be identified?

or may themselves introduce new threat scenarios. So, the residual risk must be calculated with CRA that considers the treatment actions.

Q6 How can the risk threshold and mitigations be identified?

2.7. Summary of the Challenges in CRA

Within the CRA process, most of the tasks are informal and the expertise of those who perform a CRA is of paramount importance while scientific rigor is challenged by questions which have no solution nowadays. Regardless of the expertise of whoever performs a CRA, most of the choices and inputs required along the process cannot be properly evaluated and one wonders if the results obtained give a false sense of (in)security. One knows that a new vulnerability can always be discovered, and that the likelihood and impact estimations can be radically different if one did not forget this or that (detail of a) vulnerability. However, *CRA is still the main resource to protect companies and their technologies*, and penetration testing and vulnerability assessment are useful sources of data for CRA's vulnerabilities definition but serve a different purpose.

3. Addressing the Challenges

3.1. Q1 - Cybersecurity Requirements

The first question raised was: what are the cybersecurity requirements and how do they differ from other requirements? Cybersecurity aims at protecting a system from misuses (both intentional and unintentional) and cybersecurity requirements usually focus on:

- 1) generation of data: secret or structured,
- 2) use of data to provide
 - a) integrity (using hash) and confidentiality (using symmetric encryption),
 - b) authenticity (using asymmetric encryption for signing data) and authorization (using encryption),
- 3) availability of data.

However, which of this properties makes a system cybersecure seems to be rooted in the system one considers. In our running example (i.e., the cable), which properties should one choose to make the system cybersecure? Given that secrecy is a requirement of passwords, secrets, keys, passphrases, or that confidentiality requires keeping some data hidden from non-authorized access: how would any of those properties make a cable cybersecure? A cable may

Figure 8: Cable Model - dots (data at-rest) and dashed line (data in-transit) represent the functional view, while the continuous line the physical view. The two dots represent both the functional and the physical ends of the cable, linking the functional and physical architecture.

be misused by, e.g., tampering the cable and sniffing or altering the data in-transit over the cable. This threat is related *not* to a missing requirement for the cable itself, but due to a missing requirement on the usage of such cable (i.e., *over the environment* where the cable is employed). If the cable is employed in such places where sensitive data are exchanged over the cable, then the confidentiality of such data is required. We then extend our cybersecurity investigation not just to the physical architecture of the cable but also to the functional architecture employed in the data exchanged. From the abstract model of the cable in Figure 8, we can define the following requirement.

GSR1 [General System Requirement] The cable allows the data exchange (equality between data input and data output), and the data during the exchange is called data in-transit while the data input and output are data at-rest.

As it does not consider any of the cybersecurity properties above, this requirement cannot be considered a cybersecurity requirement. To “extend” this requirement with cybersecurity requirements, we want to proceed scientifically, from a (scientific) hypothesis on what cybersecurity is. As the main - currently accepted - cybersecurity scientific theory is based on the concept of secrecy, as defined in Shannon’s theory of entropy [32], we build a structure of cybersecurity requirements (i.e., a cybersecurity theory) based on Shannon’s theory, giving a justification of the limitations and completeness of our cybersecurity theory.

Secrecy. In Shannon’s theory [32], entropy is a measure of the information generated by an information source (and then of the sequence of data exchanged over our cable). High entropy is associated to random data generation or, more precisely, to an information source that generates unpredictable information. In turn, this means that we cannot identify patterns that would allow us to predict what the information source is going to produce next. On the contrary, low entropy means that the information, produced by an information source, is highly structured; and we can identify patterns in the information produced, predicting or expecting what the information source is going to produce.

R1 [**Secret Data**] Data is secret when produced by a high-entropy information source.

R2 [**Structured Data**] Data is structured when produced by a low-entropy information source.

More formally, the *Data* type structure is the following, where the right-hand side - RHS - of the $::$ determines the

type of the terms its left-hand side - LHS,

Secret :: *Data*
Structured :: *Data*

where *Secret* and *Structured* are sub-types of *Data*. We use lower case to express an instance of the type represented by the capital case.

Let $entropy : Data \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$ be a real function which maps *Data* to a non-negative real number called *entropy*. Let c be a real threshold value, *data* is called *secret* or high-entropy with respect of c when $entropy(data) > c$ and *structured* or low-entropy when $entropy(structured) < c$. Shannon's entropy $H = -k \sum_i p_i \log_2 p_i$ is a measure of the entropy of an information source, where n is the number of possible different output symbols and p_i with $0 \leq i \leq n$ is the probability of the i -th symbol and k is a real positive constant. For the sake of simplicity, we shall omit k and the base 2 to indicate the binary logarithm. A perfectly secret information source is the one with maximum entropy, hence generates strings from a set of symbols taken from a uniform probability space over an alphabet of n symbols (i.e., each symbol i has a probability $p_i = 1/n$) and entropy is $H = -np_i \log p_i = -n \frac{1}{n} \log \frac{1}{n} = \log n$ which is 1 in the case of randomly generated bit. On the contrary, a perfectly structured information source has minimum entropy when there is only one symbol i that occurs with probability $p_i = 1$ with entropy $H = 0$ but we consider any non-secret information source as structured (more structured than a secret information source).

Confidentiality. Confidentiality (as in Shannon's theory of secrecy [33]) of data preserves the concealment of data, as secrecy, but further requires that the data are concealed from anyone but a number of trusted agents. Secrecy can be seen as a special case of confidentiality where the set of trusted agents is empty. Symmetric encryption preserves the concealment of data as long as the symmetric encryption key is only known by a number (> 0) of trusted agents.

R3 [**Confidentiality**] A symmetric (cryptographic) encryption scheme guarantees the confidentiality of the data in-transit by allowing only those sources/destinations with the en/decryption key to exchange data (i.e., to participate to the message exchange).

Formally, where *senc*, *sdec* stands for symmetric encryption/decryption, *secret* for symmetric encryption key, and *data* some arbitrary *Data*:

Confidential :: *Data*
 $senc(Data, Secret) :: Confidential$
 $sdec(Confidential, Secret) :: Data$
 $sdec(senc(data, secret), secret) = data$

OTP (One-Time Pad) can be considered a perfect encryption scheme, meaning that no attack is possible (not even brute-force) to obtain the input data from the confidential output data, without the input encryption key. OTP can be implemented as a bitwise XOR of two inputs, a secret

key and a plaintext⁷ data, i.e. $senc(plain :: Data, key :: Secret) = xor(plain, key)$. OTP preserves the entropy of the key generation process, meaning that a *secret* key implies a *secret* output of the encryption process (see Appendix C.1). One central fact is that the entropy of any encryption scheme differs from the entropy of TRNG as the encryption scheme is limited by the length of the input key⁸. In other words, the difference between secrecy and confidentiality stems from the lowering of the entropy of the secrecy generation process to a confidentiality generation process. Let a 256 bits key, even if the encryption process is OTP, a data input with more than 256 bits would necessarily make the encryption process leak part of the input data itself.

Integrity. Confidentiality is defined as the process where " k encrypts m " for k and m a cryptographic key and a plaintext respectively. Its opposite is the process of *verifying* that m is encrypted with k . Cryptographic Hash Functions are convenient functions for integrity as they "embed" the entropy of the key into their functional architecture at the cost of being deterministic (an encryption process may not be deterministic). The logic of the Hash function and the plaintext message suffice to verify that the output of an information source implementing an Hash function has actually computed the Hash on an input message. More formally, $hash(m).m'$ allows for an integrity verification process because $Pr(hash(m) = hash(m') | m \neq m') < c$ where c is an accepted probability threshold (as the key length in the case of encryption used for integrity).

Integrity is often defined as the property that preserves the unchangeability of data by means of cryptographic hash functions. In other words, integrity guarantees that the conditional probability of a successful integrity verification process, given the data and the hash, is as high as possible. Confidentiality, on the contrary, requires that the conditional entropy of the decryption process, given the plaintext data and the encrypted one, is high, not to allow any peer (without the proper key) to understand the meaning of the encrypted data (not to be able to verify any correspondence with any possible plaintext data). What we could call as perfect confidentiality results in data that not even the one who generates the data itself could understand. This equates with the concept of secrecy as high-entropy of information.

R4 [**Integrity**] A cryptographic hash function guarantees the integrity of the data (intact data) in-transit by allowing the sources/destinations to verify the equality between the hashed data in-transit and the hash of the expected plaintext data.

7. Here plaintext can be any data (secret or structured) and plaintext just wants to make a distinction between the two inputs as the key must be secret while the plaintext may not.

8. One may speculate over an infinite encryption key but all current implementations, such as AES, have an encryption key finite in length.

Formally, where *concat* stands for concatenation⁹

Intact :: *Data*
concat(Data, Data) :: *Structured*
hash(Data) :: *Secret*
concat(hash(Data), Data) :: *Intact*
hash(data) = hash(data') \iff *data = data'*

Since *hash(Data)* :: *Secret*, and, in the implementations, the number of possible hashes is less than the number of possible input data, so the hash function maps many data into the same hash. For this reason, the exact implication states *hash(data) = hash(data')* \Leftarrow *data = data'*. However, given the enormity of the possible hashes (2^{256} for sha256), we consider *hash(data) = hash(data')* \iff *data = data'*.

Authorization. Authorization supports confidentiality requires that *only* authorized peers can read the data in-transit. This can be achieved using asymmetric encryption. If the confidentiality of some data is guaranteed by using symmetric encryption, one can share the (symmetric) encrypted data, along with the symmetric encryption key re-encrypted with the recipient's public key, to an authorized peer. However, the use of asymmetric encryption achieves the same goal without compromising the confidentiality of the encryption key.

R5 [**Authorization**] An authorization scheme guarantees that the data in-transit can only be read by trusted recipients. A recipient, with its private encryption key reads what the sender encrypted with the public key of the recipient.

pk(Data) :: *Secret* \wedge *Intact*
pvt(Data) :: *Secret* \wedge *Confidential*
inv(pk(Data)) = pvt(Data)
aenc(Data, Secret \wedge *Intact)* :: *Authorized*
adec(Confidential, Secret \wedge *Confidential)* :: *Data*
adec(pvt(data'), aenc(data, pk(data'))) = *data*

where *pk* and *pvt* are respectively the public and private key, *inv* is the usual notation to relate the two, and both the types at the right and left-hand side of the \wedge symbol holds for the term on the left-hand side of the ::. As confidentiality and integrity predicate over the conditional probability of an input-output relations and the secrecy property over the generation of the outputs, no inconsistency is raised when requiring secrecy along with either confidentiality or integrity.

Authenticity. With authenticity, considered over a cable, one wants only authorized peers to be able to alter the data. As authorization requires that only authorized peers can read the data in-transit, authenticity and authorization can be seen as the same requirement over two different views of the same property: those being reading and writing

the data. So, authorization and authentication respectively predicate over the read and write access to the data. While the read of sensitive data by unauthorized peers is secured by the pre- and post-processing of the data by cryptographic algorithms, the write cannot. Authenticity¹⁰ can be guaranteed by means of asymmetric encryption, signing the data in-transit and sending a signed version of the data in-transit (along with the non-signed data). The recipient can verify if the signed data preserved its integrity while in transit.

R6 [**Authenticity**] A signature scheme (by means of asymmetric encryption) guarantees the authenticity of the data in-transit by allowing (authorizing) the recipients with the public encryption key of the sender to verify what only the sender with its private decryption key must have signed.

aenc(Data, Secret \wedge *Confidential)* :: *Authentic*
adec(Authentic, Secret \wedge *Intact)* :: *Data*

Combining Cybersecurity Requirements. There are various combination of the different cybersecurity properties considered so far. For example, one could encrypt what is then signed or the signed data (sign-then-encrypt, or encrypt-then-sign). The difference between the two approaches is that sign-then-encrypt preserves the confidentiality of the signature when the execution of the signature process is a sensitive information. Otherwise, the execution of the signature process is not confidential nor sensitive information. One could define several combinations as hash-sign-encrypt, for example. For the sake of readability we do not investigate all the possible combinations and we limit our cybersecurity assessment of the cable to the properties above.

Trust. Confidentiality, Integrity, Authorization, and Authenticity - as defined - rely on an implicit assumption: a first sensitive secret must be confidentially shared over the cable before those cybersecurity properties can be guaranteed. For Confidentiality and Authorization we need a shared secret, for Integrity and Authentication we need the data to be verified. This problem cannot be solved, as proved in [24], and then the insecurity of the first secret exchanged must be accepted and introduces the notion of trust. Therefore,

R7 [**Trust**] A trusted process must be in place to share secrets (symmetric keys) or data to enable confidentiality or integrity of the data in-transit.

Availability. The only cybersecurity property left is availability. Availability can only be tested, as we are moving further away from the concept of data, toward the material concept of the cable's physical signal. So, *confidentiality and authorization can be enforced, integrity and authenticity verified, availability tested*. As the cable is not a software but an hardware component, its availability can first be considered physical availability. Given that the physical cable can itself be altered, how can we guarantee the

9. We could have used a general function for structuring data but concatenation is widely used in the infosec domain.

10. When we write that authenticity can be guaranteed or preserved, we mean, from now on, that its verification can be done.

availability of the data exchange? Insecure (not confidential and not integrity-preserving) availability testing processes, such as PING-ing (using the ICMP protocol) the other end of the cable, can always be fooled over a tampered cable. A cybersecurity-preserving test and can be achieved using an authentication protocol. Therefore, we introduce the following requirements.

R8 [**Availability**] An authentication protocol must be used to test the availability of the two ends of the data exchange. Availability requires integrity but must also require confidentiality when the availability test itself (the fact of performing an availability test) is sensitive.

Using an authentication protocol we do not consider the functional availability of the other end but only its physical availability. In other words, we can test if the other end is alive but we cannot be sure whether or not it can provide its services. A test of the availability of the services would result in a verification of the physical and functional architecture of the two ends of the cable. Such test is impossible when one wants to verify the functional requirements (as extensional properties) against the functional architecture of the two ends (due to the Rice theorem [29]). Otherwise, if we'd detail further the inner architecture (with new intensional properties) of the components of our architecture, we would merely replicate the cybersecurity requirements defined so far (confidentiality, integrity, authorization, authentication) over the data exchange between those (newly introduced) architectural components. The availability of the functionalities of an architecture, even tough impossible to prove in general, is related not to the read or write access to the data but to their *exec*-utability. Integrity, Confidentiality, Authenticity, Authorization, all rely on the *exec* access to the cryptographic means employed to preserve them, but their objective is not to guarantee the executability of some functionalities; which is, instead, the objective of availability.

Cybersecurity and Non-cybersecurity Requirements.

We have, so far, defined the cybersecurity requirements for the cable, once the nominal non-cybersecurity (behavioral) requirement was defined (i.e., to exchange data); addressing Q1. One may still wonder if we considered all the cybersecurity properties needed to make a cable cybersecurity. We summarize the approach to the requirements as follows.

- 1) We defined cybersecurity based on the concept of information entropy (discretized into low and high entropy).
- 2) The definition of secure data has been related not just to the essential properties of being structured, secret, or confidential information (solely depending on their entropy), but also to the verifiability of its content (integrity and authenticity as high and low conditional entropy) and to the testing of its availability by means of authentication protocols. This encompasses the read, write, and *exec* access to data.
- 3) An overview of the structure of properties considered in this section is provided in Figure 9.

As a mathematical interpretation of those properties is only sketched, we cannot guarantee that we considered all

Figure 9: Cybersecurity Properties

the cybersecurity properties and this is envisioned as future work. With this review of cybersecurity requirements and properties we want to pave the way for such future work and to provide a reference list of (supposedly complete) cybersecurity requirements over a minimal reference example. We hope that this will be of help to compare future formalization of cybersecurity risk assessment methodologies.

3.2. Q2 - Threat Identification

The threat identification phase usually considers the following concepts:

- A *Threat*, as defined in [4], is “Any circumstance or event with the potential to adversely impact organizational operations (including mission, functions, image, or reputation), organizational assets, individuals, other organizations, or the Nation through an information system via unauthorized access, destruction, disclosure, modification of information, and/or denial of service”.
- *Vulnerability*¹¹, as defined in [4] (and adopted in [20]), is “*weakness* in an information system, system security procedures, internal controls, or implementation that could be exploited by a threat source”.
- An *Exploit*¹² “[...] (from the English verb to exploit, meaning to use something to one’s own advantage) is a piece of software, a chunk of data, or a sequence of commands that takes advantage of a bug or vulnerability to cause unintended or unanticipated behavior to occur on computer software, hardware, or something electronic (usually computerized).” [41].
- An *Attack*, as defined by the International Standard ISO/IEC 27000 is an “attempt to destroy, expose, alter, disable, steal or gain unauthorized access to or make unauthorized use of an asset”; where an *Asset* is “anything that has value to the organization”.

All the above definitions lacks a formal ground but provide a general understanding of what cyber-insecurities are. Cyber-insecurities can be considered as the set of all threats,

11. The term vulnerability is not present in the Encyclopedia of Cryptography and Security, while it is used in 12 entries

12. The term exploit is only used as a verb in [15]

vulnerabilities, etc. as all those terms mean to prevent *some* (potentially) unexpected behaviors of a system. However, unexpected behaviors are not necessarily in-secure behaviors. By chance, some unexpected behaviors may be secure behaviors (maybe unsafe behaviors) meaning that no cybersecurity requirement is negatively impacted.

Definition 1. A cyber-insecure system is the one which shows unexpected behaviors that negatively impacts on some cybersecurity requirements. A cyber-secure system is a system that does not have unexpected behaviors (sufficient), or a system where the unexpected behaviors do not negatively impact cybersecurity requirements.

In the previous section, we listed the cybersecurity requirements and now we can categorize all the unexpected behaviors over the impact they would have on the cybersecurity requirements; by negating all the cybersecurity requirements we obtain all the cyber-insecurity categories which we call threats.

Definition 2. A threat is the negation of a cybersecurity requirement. The set of all the cybersecurity requirements (GSRI-R8) is justified as a structure of infosec properties based on Shannon’s theory of information. The set of all the threats is the set of all negated requirements.

All the unexpected behaviors which do not impact the cybersecurity requirements are functional or logical bugs (or faults) in the implementation of the functional/physical architecture into the software/hardware components. The distinction between the terms weakness, threat, vulnerability, attack, exploit, provides an understanding of the causal relation connecting a weakness to an exploit, as follows.

- 1) A **weakness** (e.g., the lack of a requirement) is:
 - a) a **bug** when it impacts a system requirement,
 - b) a **threat** when it impacts a cybersecurity requirement (e.g., non-confidential data in-transit, negating R3),
- 2) Threats leads to a **threat scenario or vulnerability** as an effect on the system that the threat causes (e.g., impacting the confidentiality of a secret used in an encryption process),
- 3) leading to an **attack** (pattern) when the vulnerability can be **exploited** by a threat actor.

Summarizing, a threat finds its opposite in what is required for the cybersecurity of a system. In turn, if a system is cybersecure, its behavior is expected, or its architectural components are known to perform only the expected behaviors¹³. Therefore, the negation of all the requirements determines all the possible threats (answering to Q2) if the completeness of the requirements can be proved. It is, however, impossible – in general – to prove the completeness of the requirements when behavioral properties are defined as extensional properties (Rice theorem). An extensional property (or external question/desiderata/requirement) is [3] “concerning the existence or reality of the system of entities

as a whole” (e.g., statements such as: this system calculates the function F). Therefore, for the completeness of the threats (and for the consistency of the speculations over the results of a risk assessment), a threat assessment shall only consider (and be limited to) intensional requirements. An intensional property (or internal question/desiderata/requirement) predicates the existence of a certain entity (element or architecture) within the linguistic framework, for the representation of the architecture (e.g., statements such as: the system has 32bit registers) of a system. As the intensional requirements defined in the above section are all possible cybersecurity *over* a nominal requirement, the negation of the cybersecurity requirements determines the whole set of cyber-insecurities sub-divided into threats categories, but this is true:

- 1) as long as the law of information entropy and Shannon’s theory is the correct cybersecurity “frame of reference”. To the best of our knowledge, *no other theory predicts all the cybersecurity requirements defined in the previous section;*
- 2) but limited to negatively impacting only the nominal behaviors defined. The definition of all the nominal behaviors encompasses both intensional and extensional properties. While intensional properties can be formally proved, the definition of nominal behaviors as extensional properties will always lack a general formal proof (as per Rice theorem).

Threat Assessment of the Cable. The first three requirements determines which types of data, as building blocks of the abstract cybersecure architecture of the system (the secure cable), *we must distinguish*. First, data at-rest must be distinguished from data in-transit but, in our running example so far, we only considered data in-transit. We leave the discussion on data at-rest for later as it would unnecessarily complicate the flow of the paper. So, *data in-transit* is called:

- *secret*, when the information source generating it produces high-entropy information,
- *structured*, when the information source generating it produces low-entropy information,

Data in-transit can be *sensitive* or *non-sensitive* and we may have secret-sensitive and secret-non-sensitive, or structured-sensitive and structured-non-sensitive information. We must include here the possible combination with confidential, authorized, authentic, or integrity preserving data, but we omit listing them for readability. The term *sensitive*, as a predicate over data in-transit, relates to confidentiality/authorization, while no predicate has been defined yet that relates to integrity/authenticity and structured information. We call such property *accountability*: the property that determines *accountable* data through authenticity. Accountable and sensitive data cannot be part of the formalization of cybersecurity properties as data are determined as accountable or sensitive based on factors which are not related to the engineering field. As an example, sensitive data can be the design of a new product which one wants to keep confidential (and, e.g., authentic too). This data is

13. We have here defined cybersecurity in a positive way, stating when a system is cyber-secure, instead of defining cybersecurity as limiting concept as when it is related to insecurities.

justified as sensitive based on potential negative impacts on assets such as trades, investments, revenue, etc. (i.e., which are not the system itself) of threats that makes the data non-confidential (i.e., data leakage); an investigation of this relation (sensitivity-threat) is in Section 3.2.1. The first threat is then:

T1 The misclassification of one of the possible data types: secret, structured, sensitive, non-sensitive, accountable, non-accountable data, as negation of R1, R2 and of the derived requirements on the identification of sensitive and accountable data¹⁴.

The negation of the requirements defines the threats list, but the union of the requirements defines a **policy** (i.e., a policy is a set of requirements and defines a cyber-secure system or sub-system). To mitigate T1, a data classification policy must then require that all the data are labeled with the corresponding data type. This policy comes with the threat of data misclassification but what is its risk? What is its impact and likelihood? Before moving to the next question (Q3) we list all the other threats obtained as negations of the requirements defined in the above section. We also relate each threat with a mitigating policy (and we give a reference to the corresponding policy definition in the ISO 27001:2022 Annex A).

T2 R3 threat: “the symmetric encryption scheme does not guarantee data confidentiality.” Reference policy: cryptography policy (ISO 27001:2022 - A.8.24).

T3 R4 threat: “the cryptographic hash function does not guarantee data integrity.” Reference policy: cryptography policy (ISO 27001:2022 - A.8.24).

T4 R5 threat: “the access control scheme does not guarantee confidentiality.” Reference policy: access control policy (ISO 27001:2022 - A.5.15).

T5 R6 threat: “the signature scheme does not guarantee authenticity.” Reference policy: authentication policy (ISO 27001:2022 - A.8.5).

T6 R7 threat: “the first secret is not shared with a trusted process.” Reference policy: information transfer policy (ISO 27001:2022 - A.5.14).

T7 R8 threat: “an authentication protocol is not used to test the availability of the ends of the cables; or the confidentiality of the availability test is not guaranteed.” The ISO 27001 reference policy for availability is usually considered to be the “redundancy of information processing facilities (ISO 27001:2022 - A.8.14)” but redundant systems can all be compromised if availability, as we defined, is not guaranteed.

The general system requirement GSR1 states the behavior of the system (cable), we could negate it obtaining the following threat.

GST1 the cable does not allow the data exchange.

14. We don't explicitly have confidentiality, integrity, authorization, and authentication considered in this requirement but they are all subsumed by sensitive and accountable data. We will consider this requirement more in details later in Section 3.2.1.

Note that this does *not* constitute a *cybersecurity* threat, since it does not impact a *cybersecurity* requirement, but we report it here for the sake of completeness of the discussion.

3.2.1. Impact of the Threat Scenarios. The answer to the question Q2 that we gave above is only partial. We listed a set of threats and we justified its completeness over a structure of requirements and cybersecurity properties but, in the question, we also raised the challenge of identifying vulnerabilities and defining policies. If threats are negation of requirements, vulnerabilities put the threat in the context of the system under analysis. The context is the cable under attack so a vulnerability must consider both the system (the cable) and describe the threat as a vulnerability over the system. *Vulnerabilities are interpretations of threats over a system.* Similarly, policies frame a cybersecurity requirement in the context where the system itself is used (e.g., a company).

T1.1 - Misclassification. Let us analyze the first type of the misclassification threat T1: secret misclassification. A secret is high-entropy information (see [32]) meaning that by reading the outputs of the information source, one can predict the next output with the highest possible probability or $\frac{1}{|O|}$, where $|O|$ is the cardinality of the set of possible outputs. Therefore, the Information Classification Policy (ISO 27001:2022 A.5.12) must encompass the following requirement (for the full policy see Appendix A).

- Policy Requirement 1: Classification of secrets.
- Derived Requirement: symbols of a secret are predicted with probability $\frac{1}{|O|}$ and a secret of length n is predicted with a probability of $\frac{1}{|O|^n}$.
- Threat: T1.1 - misclassification of secrets.
- Vulnerability: a symbol of a secret is likely to be predicted (or guessed) when the the probability greater than $\frac{1}{|O|}$

The analysis of the policies related to the threats T2–T7 reach a result similar to the one just obtained for T1. Instead, the negative result obtained analyzing the nominal requirement GSR1 as a threat (we remind that GST1 is not a threat), allows for a broader consideration, paving the way for a distinction between what is meant by likelihood and impact, which is the focus of the next two sections (Section 3.4 and Section 3.5).

3.3. Likelihood and Impact

As all the cybersecurity requirements aim at preserving (necessary but not sufficient condition) GSR1, i.e., the nominal behavior of the cable, we may ask for justifications of why GSR1 and not any other nominal requirement. The answer to this question is found beyond the cable itself, in the processes that use the cable. In a business, e.g., selling the cable, a negative impact on the requirement GSR1 translates to an impact on revenue, reputation, etc. of the company selling the cable. In the latter (i.e., impact

on the on the revenue¹⁵) the term “impact” is used as an extensional property, meaning that predicates *over* the cable, *on* the (business) processes that *use* the cable. This impact, as it considers the cable *not* in its architecture (in its essence) but as a *use* value, implicitly stating that any threat that impacts the nominal behavior of the cable also impacts the processes using it (the revenue). While specifying the impact on the cybersecurity requirements gives further details on the causality relation between the threats and the revenue, the last step of the impact causality chain (requirement → threat → processes → revenue), the impact is ultimately always the same per each cybersecurity requirement and threat: the revenue. By the same way of reasoning, the likelihood of an impact on the revenue is undefined if considered an extensional property; as likelihood should consider factors external to the cable (i.e., even assuming a perfect cable) that impact on the revenue, such as market instability. Instead, all the intensionally-defined threats have their own formally-definable likelihood, and they impact, ultimately, the revenue. We stress *the gap between the formal threat assessment (over threats and intensional requirements of a system) and the risk assessment (over the processes using a system, and their aim)*.

3.4. Q3 - Likelihood Calculation

For the estimation of the likelihood of threats, we adopt a “worst case scenario” approach, assuming: if something bad can happen, it will happen.

Definition 3. *The likelihood of a threat is high/low if a threat can/cannot happen.*

Definition 4. *A risk is the negation of a nominal requirement, while a threat is the negation of a cybersecurity requirement (as per Definition 2).*

Definition 5. *The likelihood of a risk, is the ratio between the unmitigated threats (cannot happen; i.e., the enforced cybersecurity requirements) and the possible ones (can happen; i.e., non-enforced cybersecurity requirements).*

Therefore, a (non-mitigated, possible) *threat increases the likelihood that a risk, as the negation of a nominal requirement, may impact the revenue/processes*. So, we identified (from a formal structure of cybersecurity properties) an enumerable, finite set of threats (categories) which can be used as a (e.g., uniform) probability space over which the likelihood is calculated. We have then answered **Q3**, assuming the completeness of the structure of cybersecurity properties defined in Section 3.1 and related threats.

In Figure 10 we show the threat assessment and in Figure 11 the risk assessment and we now describe and justify the results in these two figures. The likelihood of the risk is calculated as the total number of the possible threats (i.e., threats with high likelihood). More formally the *likelihood*

15. We acknowledge that other company assets, such as reputation, could be considered here; but, as the definition of this assets uses extensional requirements, we consider revenue as representative for all the others.

of the *risks* is calculated as $\sum_{i=1}^n likelihood(t_i)$ where the predicate *likelihood()* is 1 (or *True*¹⁶) iff its argument has high likelihood, 0 (or *False*) otherwise.

3.5. Q4 - Impact Calculation

The concept of impact must be articulated over the two different concepts described in Section 3.3: impact of the threats and impact of the risk(s).

Impact of the threats. Threats impact the cybersecurity requirements (secrecy, integrity, confidentiality, ...) defined in Section 3.1. Therefore, a *qualitative* definition of impact determines *which* cybersecurity requirements are impacted by a threat while a *quantitative* impact assessment calculates *how many* cybersecurity requirements are impacted by a threat. Based on the 7 threats (T1–T7, excluding GST1 which is not impacting a cybersecurity requirement), in Figure 10, we show how each threat impacts one or more of the cybersecurity requirements (R1–R8), both qualitatively and quantitatively. Finally, we can limit the quantitative impact of the threats as $1 \leq impact(t_i) \leq 8$.

Impact of the risk. A risk (negation of the nominal requirement GST1) impacts the company (the revenue) but this type of impact, as we already mentioned, cannot be intensionally defined. The impact of a risk can be formally defined only if it is related to the impact of the threats.

Definition 6. *The impact of a risk is qualitatively defined as the relation between the union of the cybersecurity properties impacted and the effect on the business (revenue); quantitatively by the number of those cybersecurity properties.*

In Figure 11, we quantitatively estimate the impact as the sum of all the cybersecurity requirements, impacted by the threats, that, in turn, negatively impact the assets (i.e., revenue and processes), creating a risk (i.e., “the cable does not allow the data exchange”) for the requirement GSRI. Formally: $\sum_{i=1}^n impact(t_i)$. By considering both the impact of threats and of risk, we answered to **Q4**. However, one may wonder why the *sum* of the impacted cybersecurity requirements and not, say, the *multiplication*, is the correct quantitative estimate of the impact of the threats. We consider each threat as an event *independent* from the other threats and we assume a worst case scenario where each threat is an element of a uniform probability distribution.

3.6. Q5 - Risk Calculation

The quantitative evaluation of the risk is related to the impact and likelihood of the threats. Intuitively, the higher/lower the impact and likelihood, the higher/lower the risk. In Figure 11, we have 7 different threats (out of 7 possible threats), potentially impacting 12 times on the 8 cybersecurity requirements. As all the threats are possible in our running example (i.e., no one has been mitigated yet), the likelihood of an impact on the asset of one of

16. Using the standard mapping between boolean values and integers.

ID	Threat ID	Thread description	Qualitative impact	Quantitative impact	Likelihood (HIGH/LOW)
TA1	T1	misclassification of one of the six possible data types	All R1–R8	8	HIGH
TA2	T2	symmetric encryption scheme does not guarantee data confidentiality	Confidentiality R3	1	HIGH
TA3	T3	cryptographic hash function does not guarantee data integrity	Integrity R4	1	HIGH
TA4	T4	access control scheme does not guarantee confidentiality	Authorization R5	1	HIGH
TA5	T5	signature scheme does not guarantee authenticity	Authenticity R6	1	HIGH
TA6	T6	first secret not shared with a trusted process	Trust R7	1	HIGH
TA7	T7	authentication protocol not used to test the availability	Availability R8	1	HIGH

Figure 10: Cybersecurity Threat Assessment

ID	Qualitative Analysis		Quantitative Analysis					
	Risk (Asset)	Impact (Asset)	Risk (Threats)	Max Risk (Threats)	Impact (Threats)	Max Impact (Threats)	Likelihood (Threats)	Max Likelihood (Threats)
RA1	No data exchange	Revenue/Processes	96	96	12	12	8	8

Figure 11: Cybersecurity Risk Assessment

the possible threats is $\frac{7}{7} = 1$ (i.e., if an agent wants to attack the cable, it will, regardless of the threat chosen). As we have $\frac{12}{12}$ possible impacts (of the threats over the cybersecurity properties), with probability/likelihood 1, any (not all) possible impact can be realized; this is the *highest* possible cybersecurity risk and we answered to Q5.

3.7. Q6 - Mitigation Strategy

The objective of the mitigation strategy is identify and prioritize the business and technical enforcements that reduce the likelihood or impact of the risks and threats. In our running example, we only considered one risk and the prioritization of the risks has little meaning in this context. However, the prioritization of the risk can be both based on the type of impact/assets of the risks or by the quantitative estimations of the risks. In the first case, no formal definition can be identified as the reasons behind the prioritization cannot be justified against a scientific hypothesis. The second case, requires further investigation as it cannot be merely based on the highest value calculated as risk, impact, or likelihood quantitative estimations. Instead, as usually done by the industry, it must consider the qualitative estimations of those estimations. As we only have one risk, the qualitative estimation of the impact of the risk on the assets would either result in having the risk as having the highest priority (must be mitigated) or the lowest (no mitigation required). We assume the risk must be mitigated, to continue with our reasoning. The quantitative risk assessment of the threats impacting the only one risk RA1 (Figure 11), tells us *how many* cybersecurity properties each threats impacts but the relations between the different cybersecurity properties remains hidden in this quantitative assessment. In other words, a mitigation strategy should also consider that without mitigating one threat we cannot mitigate others. For example, if one mitigates the threat on confidentiality T2 but not the threat on the classification of data T1, one may still not be able to guarantee the confidentiality of what is actually confidential (not encrypting some of the confidential data) or vice-versa, wasting resources on encrypting non-confidential data. To address this, we want to consider the *effort* and the *gain* of mitigating a threat, as follows.

Figure 12: Gain-Effort Graph

- Effort: the number of derived requirements to be enforced by the mitigation of a threat.
- Gain: the number of threats benefited from a mitigation.

In Figure 12, we take the structure of cybersecurity properties in Figure 9 and provide a graph structure of connected properties, along with the quantitative estimation of gain and effort, calculated as follows. Each node of the graph (each property) has an out-degree (number of outgoing edges) that represents the other cybersecurity properties upon which the node depends. For example, *integrity* depends upon the structured and secrecy nodes. The in-degree (number of incoming edge) of each node represents the cybersecurity properties which *directly* depends upon the node considered. For example, *authenticity* and *authorization* depends upon *integrity*. So, the *gain* of integrity is related to the sub-graph of all the nodes that have a path towards integrity (e.g., availability, authenticity, and authorization all has a path that reaches integrity) and $gain(N) = \sum_{i \in subgraph(N)} inDegree(i)$. Similarly, the effort is related to the whole out-degree (the number of nodes reachable by a node, e.g., integrity). Finally, we define a *mitigation strategy* based on *lowest effort and highest gain* as in Figure 12, and the *risk threshold* is the maximum priority¹⁷ to be mitigated, answering to Q6.

17. As is typical, priorities are arranged in reverse order, so priority 1 is *higher* than priority 3

4. Conclusion

We provided a detailed overview of the cybersecurity risk assessment process, defining a methodology justified by a structure of cybersecurity properties. Some of the mainstream concepts in the field of risk assessment turned out to have a non-trivial definition. Some examples are (i) the concept of availability which we enforced with authentication protocols, (ii) the concept of risk threshold that has been justified with a gain-effort graph, and (iii) the extensional and intensional definitions of risk. As the whole methodology is built over a structure of cybersecurity properties (here sketched not because of lack of space but due to a lack of knowledge at the very logical foundation of the concept of cybersecurity), the authors hope that this formalization offers insights towards a more precise definition.

References

- [1] Information Security Forum (ISF). *Information risk assessment methodology 2 (IRAM2)*. 2024. URL: <https://www.securityforum.org/solutions-and-insights/information-risk-assessment-methodology-2-iram2/>.
- [2] Richard A Caralli et al. “Introducing octave allegro: Improving the information security risk assessment process”. In: *Hanscom AFB, MA* (2007).
- [3] Rudolf Carnap. “Empiricism, semantics, and ontology”. In: *Revue internationale de philosophie* (1950), pp. 20–40.
- [4] Committee on National Security Systems (CNSS). *Glossary No 4009*. Tech. rep. Apr. 2015. URL: <https://rmf.org/wp-content/uploads/2017/10/CNSSI-4009.pdf>.
- [5] CVSS: *Common Vulnerability Scoring System Calculator*. URL: <https://nvd.nist.gov/vuln-metrics/cvss/v3-calculator>.
- [6] Premier Ministre) DCSSI (Direction Centrale de la Sécurité des Systèmes d’Information. *EBIOS (Expression des Besoins et Identification des Objectifs de Sécurité)*. 2004. URL: https://www.enisa.europa.eu/topics/risk-management/current-risk/risk-management-inventory/rm-ra-methods/m_ebios.html.
- [7] Steven De Haes, Van Grembergen Wim, and Debrecen Roger S. “OBIT 5 and enterprise governance of information technology: Building blocks and research opportunities”. In: *Journal of Information Systems* 27 (1 2013).
- [8] ENISA. *MAGERIT*. 2005. URL: https://www.enisa.europa.eu/topics/risk-management/current-risk/risk-management-inventory/rm-ra-methods/m_magerit.html.
- [9] I GNM Putra Eryawana, Gusti M Arya Sasmitaa, and AA KT Agung Cahyawan. “NIST SP 800-30”. In: (2012).
- [10] NIST Joint Task Force. *Security and Privacy Controls for Information Systems and Organizations (NIST SP 800-53 Rev. 5)*. 2020. URL: <https://csrc.nist.gov/publications/detail/sp/800-%2053/rev-5/final>.
- [11] Rajni Goel, Anupam Kumar, and James Haddow. “PRISM: a strategic decision framework for cybersecurity risk assessment”. In: *Information & Computer Security* 28.4 (2020), pp. 591–625.
- [12] Donald Good. *The Foundations of Computer Security - We Need Some*. Sept. 1986. URL: <https://www.ieee-security.org/CSFWweb/goodessay.html> (visited on 11/09/2022).
- [13] Cormac Herley. “Unfalsifiability of security claims”. en. In: *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 113.23 (June 2016), pp. 6415–6420. ISSN: 0027-8424, 1091-6490. DOI: [10.1073/pnas.1517797113](https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1517797113). URL: <https://pnas.org/doi/full/10.1073/pnas.1517797113> (visited on 10/28/2022).
- [14] Cormac Herley and P.C. Van Oorschot. “SoK: Science, Security and the Elusive Goal of Security as a Scientific Pursuit”. In: *2017 IEEE Symposium on Security and Privacy (SP)*. San Jose, CA: IEEE, May 2017, pp. 99–120. ISBN: 978-1-5090-5533-3. DOI: [10.1109/SP.2017.38](https://doi.org/10.1109/SP.2017.38). URL: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/7958573/> (visited on 11/30/2022).
- [15] ISO IEC. “Information technology—Security techniques—Information security management systems—Overview and vocabulary”. In: *International Standard No. ISO/IEC 27000* (2012), p. 32.
- [16] ThreatModeler Software Inc. *ThreatModeler Software*. 2024. URL: <https://threatmodeler.com/threatmodeler/#threatmodeler>.
- [17] Federal Office for Information Security (Germany). *IT-Grundschutz Standards and Certification*. 2020. URL: https://www.bsi.bund.de/EN/Themen/Unternehmen-und-Organisationen/Standards-und-Zertifizierung/IT-Grundschutz/it-grundschutz_node.html.
- [18] Joint Task Force Transformation Initiative et al. *SP 800-39. managing information security risk: Organization, mission, and information system view*. National Institute of Standards & Technology, 2011.
- [19] Center for Internet Security (CIS). *CIS Critical Security Controls*. 2018. URL: <https://www.cisecurity.org/controls>.
- [20] Joint Task Force Interagency Working Group. *Security and Privacy Controls for Information Systems and Organizations*. Tech. rep. Edition: Revision 5. National Institute of Standards and Technology, Sept. 2020. DOI: [10.6028/NIST.SP.800-53r5](https://nvlpubs.nist.gov/nistpubs/SpecialPublications/NIST.SP.800-53r5.pdf). URL: <https://nvlpubs.nist.gov/nistpubs/SpecialPublications/NIST.SP.800-53r5.pdf> (visited on 11/22/2023).
- [21] Bilge Karabacak and Ibrahim Sogukpinar. “ISRAM: information security risk analysis method”. In: *Computers & Security* 24.2 (2005), pp. 147–159.
- [22] Mass Soldal Lund, Bjørnar Solhaug, and Ketil Stølen. “Analysing Likelihood Using CORAS Diagrams”. en. In: *Model-Driven Risk Analysis*. Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer Berlin Heidelberg, 2011, pp. 207–244. ISBN: 978-3-642-12322-1 978-3-642-12323-8. DOI: [10.1007/978-3-642-12323-8_13](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-12323-8_13). URL: http://link.springer.com/10.1007/978-3-642-12323-8_13 (visited on 12/14/2022).
- [23] Mass Soldal Lund, Bjørnar Solhaug, and Ketil Stølen. *Model-driven risk analysis: the CORAS approach*. Springer Science & Business Media, 2010.
- [24] Ueli Maurer. “Information-Theoretically Secure Secret-Key Agreement by NOT Authenticated Public Discussion”. en. In: *Advances in Cryptology — EUROCRYPT ’97*. Ed. by Walter Fumy. Lecture Notes in Computer Science. Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer, 1997, pp. 209–225. ISBN: 978-3-540-69053-5. DOI: [10.1007/3-540-69053-0_15](https://doi.org/10.1007/3-540-69053-0_15).
- [25] Vladimir Lucian Mihailescu. “Risk analysis and risk management using MEHARI”. In: *J. Appl. Bus. Inf. Syst* 3.4 (2012), pp. 143–162.

- [26] National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST). *National Vulnerability Database (NVD) - Vulnerabilities*. URL: <https://nvd.nist.gov/vuln> (visited on 01/27/2023).
- [27] OMG. *Business Process Model and Notation (BPMN)*. Dec. 2013. URL: <https://www.omg.org/spec/BPMN/2.0.2/PDF>.
- [28] Karl Popper. *The Logic of Scientific Discovery*. en. 0th ed. Routledge, Nov. 2005. ISBN: 978-1-134-47002-0. DOI: [10.4324/9780203994627](https://www.taylorfrancis.com/books/9781134470020). URL: <https://www.taylorfrancis.com/books/9781134470020> (visited on 01/25/2023).
- [29] H. G. Rice. “Classes of recursively enumerable sets and their decision problems”. en. In: *Transactions of the American Mathematical Society* 74.2 (1953), pp. 358–366. ISSN: 0002-9947, 1088-6850. DOI: [10.1090/S0002-9947-1953-0053041-6](https://www.ams.org/tran/1953-074-02/S0002-9947-1953-0053041-6/). URL: <https://www.ams.org/tran/1953-074-02/S0002-9947-1953-0053041-6/> (visited on 11/30/2022).
- [30] Marco Rocchetto and Nils Ole Tippenhauer. “On Attacker Models and Profiles for Cyber-Physical Systems”. en. In: *Computer Security – ESORICS 2016*. Ed. by Ioannis Askoxylakis et al. Vol. 9879. Series Title: Lecture Notes in Computer Science. Cham: Springer International Publishing, 2016, pp. 427–449. ISBN: 978-3-319-45740-6 978-3-319-45741-3. DOI: [10.1007/978-3-319-45741-3_22](https://link.springer.com/10.1007/978-3-319-45741-3_22). URL: https://link.springer.com/10.1007/978-3-319-45741-3_22 (visited on 12/14/2022).
- [31] Prameet Roy. *Framework for Improving Critical Infrastructure Cybersecurity*. 2018.
- [32] C. E. Shannon. “A mathematical theory of communication”. In: *The Bell System Technical Journal* 27.3 (July 1948), pp. 379–423. ISSN: 0005-8580. DOI: [10.1002/j.1538-7305.1948.tb01338.x](https://doi.org/10.1002/j.1538-7305.1948.tb01338.x).
- [33] C. E. Shannon. “Communication Theory of Secrecy Systems”. en. In: *Bell System Technical Journal* 28.4 (Oct. 1949). Number: 4, pp. 656–715. ISSN: 00058580. DOI: [10.1002/j.1538-7305.1949.tb00928.x](https://doi.org/10.1002/j.1538-7305.1949.tb00928.x). URL: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/6769090> (visited on 08/04/2021).
- [34] Spyridon Samonas and David Coss. “The CIA strikes back: Redefining confidentiality, integrity and availability in security.” In: *Journal of Information System Security* 10.3 (2014). ISSN: 1551-0123. URL: <https://www.proso.com/dl/Samonas.pdf>.
- [35] Amril Syalim, Yoshiaki Hori, and Kouichi Sakurai. “Comparison of risk analysis methods: Mehari, magerit, NIST800-30 and microsoft’s security management guide”. In: *2009 International conference on availability, reliability and security*. IEEE, 2009, pp. 726–731.
- [36] The MITRE Corporation. *Common Vulnerabilities and Exposures (CVE)*. URL: <https://www.cve.org/> (visited on 02/02/2023).
- [37] The MITRE Corporation. *Common Weaknesses Enumeration (CWE)*. URL: <https://cwe.mitre.org/> (visited on 02/02/2023).
- [38] The MITRE Corporation. *CVE Metrics*. URL: <https://www.cve.org/About/Metrics> (visited on 05/28/2024).
- [39] Amie Thomasson. *Categories*. Ed. by Edward N. Zalta and Uri Nodelman. 2022. URL: <https://plato.stanford.edu/archives/fall2022/entries/categories/>.
- [40] Jiali Wang, Martin Neil, and Norman Fenton. “A Bayesian network approach for cybersecurity risk assessment implementing and extending the FAIR model”. In: *Computers & Security* 89 (2020), p. 101659.
- [41] Wikipedia Foundation Inc. *Exploit (computer security)*. Nov. 2019. URL: [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Exploit_\(computer_security\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Exploit_(computer_security)).
- [42] Zeki Yazar. “A qualitative risk analysis and management tool—CRAMM”. In: *SANS InfoSec Reading Room White Paper* 11.1 (2002), pp. 12–32.

Appendix

1. Information Classification Policy

- Policy: Information Classification Policy (ISO 27001:2022 A.5.12).
- Policy Requirement 1: Classification of secrets.
 - Derived Requirement: symbols of a secret are predicted with probability $\frac{1}{|O|}$ and a secret of length n is predicted with a probability of $\frac{1}{|O|^n}$.
 - Threat: T1.1 - misclassification of secrets.
 - Vulnerability: a symbol of a secret is likely to be predicted (or guessed) when the the probability greater than $\frac{1}{|O|}$
- Policy Requirement 2: Classification of structured data.
 - Derived Requirement: structured data are predicted with probability $\frac{|O|}{|O|} = 1$.
 - Threat: T1.2 - misclassification of structured data.
 - Vulnerability: a structured data is unlikely to be predicted (or guessed) when with probability lower than 1.
- Policy Requirement 3: Classification of sensitive data.
 - Derived Requirement: sensitive data are read (predictable with probability $\frac{|O|}{|O|} = 1$, i.e., are considered as structured data) by authorized peers, with probability $\frac{1}{|O|}$ (i.e., are considered secrets) by unauthorized peers.
 - Threat: T1.3 - misclassification of sensitive data.
 - Vulnerability: a sensitive data is likely (with probability lower than 1) to be read (or guessed) by an authorized peer or unlikely to be read by an unauthorized peer.
- Policy Requirement 4: Classification of accountable data.
 - Derived Requirement: accountable data are changed by authenticated peers (with probability $\frac{|O|}{|O|} = 1$ over the verification process), with probability $\frac{1}{|O|}$ by unauthorized peers.

- Threat: T1.4 - misclassification of accountable data.
- Vulnerability: an accountable data is likely (with probability lower than 1) to be changed by an authenticated peer or unlikely to be changed by an unauthorized peer.
- Policy Requirement 5 and 6: Classification of non-sensitive and non-accountable data are omitted for brevity.

2. Review of Cybersecurity Standards and Frameworks

The objective of this review is to identify a structured methodology for cybersecurity risk management.

2.1. ISO/IEC 27001 and 27002. The ISO/IEC 27000 family of standards covers a broad range of information security standards published by both the International Organization for Standardization and International Electrotechnical Commission. ISO 27000 recommends best practices for managing information risks by implementing security control within the framework of an overall Information Security Management System (ISMS). ISO/IEC 27001:2022 defines the code of practice for information security management. ISO/IEC 27001 specifies the requirements for establishing, implementing, operating, monitoring, reviewing, maintaining and improving a documented ISMS within the context of the organization's overall business risks. It specifies requirements for the implementation of security controls customized to the needs of individual organizations or parts thereof. ISO/IEC 27001 is designed to ensure the selection of adequate and proportionate security controls that protect information assets and give confidence to interested parties. ISO/IEC 27001 consists of 10 clauses (where the importance of the context of the organization, commitment of the leadership and performance evaluations are described) and Annex A, which describes 114 security measures in 14 security categories. ISO/IEC 27002 provides an in-depth description and recommendations for the implementation of the security controls of Annex A.

ISO/IEC 27000 family (and then ISO/IEC 27001, 27002) requires the conduction of risk assessments within the ISMS and describes how to conduct them in ISO/IEC 27005. The risk management process in ISO/IEC 27005, along with a finer description, are depicted in Figure 13.

2.2. NIST Cybersecurity Framework v1.1. The NIST Cybersecurity Framework v1.1. [31] is a risk-based approach to managing cybersecurity risk and is composed of three parts: the Framework Core, the Framework Implementation Tiers, and the Framework Profiles. The Core presents industry standards, guidelines, and practices in a manner that allows for communication of cybersecurity activities and outcomes across the organization from the executive level to the implementation/operations level. The Framework Core consists of five concurrent and continuous functions: Identify, Protect, Detect, Respond, Recover. As in Figure 14, these functions

Figure 13: Risk process in ISO/IEC 27005

are structured into 23 categories (similar to Annex A of ISO/IEC 27001) and 98 subcategories (similar to controls in ISO/IEC 27001 Annex A) and for each subcategory several references are made to other frameworks like ISO/IEC 27001, ISACA COBIT [7], NIST SP 800-53 [10], ISA/IEC 62443, and CIS Critical Security Controls [19].

2.3. OCTAVE Allegro. OCTAVE Allegro [2] is a methodology to streamline and optimize the process of assessing information security risks so that an organization can obtain sufficient results with a small investment in time, people, and other limited resources. It leads the organization to consider people, technology, and facilities in the context of their relationship to information and the business processes and services they support. It is intended to help an organization to address different aspects of the risk assessment process, such that:

- Develop qualitative risk evaluation criteria that describe the organization's operational risk tolerances.
- Identify assets that are important to the mission of the organization.
- Identify vulnerabilities and threats to those assets.
- Determine and evaluate the potential consequences to the organization if threats are realized.

Figure 15 illustrates the eight required steps in four phases by Octave allegro approach.

Function Unique Identifier	Function	Category Unique Identifier	Category
ID	Identify	ID.AM	Asset Management
		ID.BE	Business Environment
		ID.GV	Governance
		ID.RA	Risk Assessment
		ID.RM	Risk Management Strategy
		ID.SC	Supply Chain Risk Management
PR	Protect	PR.AC	Identity Management and Access Control
		PR.AT	Awareness and Training
		PR.DS	Data Security
		PR.IP	Information Protection Processes and Procedures
		PR.MA	Maintenance
		PR.PT	Protective Technology
DE	Detect	DE.AE	Anomalies and Events
		DE.CM	Security Continuous Monitoring
		DE.DP	Detection Processes
RS	Respond	RS.RP	Response Planning
		RS.CO	Communications
		RS.AN	Analysis
		RS.MI	Mitigation
		RS.IM	Improvements
RC	Recover	RC.RP	Recovery Planning
		RC.IM	Improvements
		RC.CO	Communications

Figure 14: The 23 categories related to the 5 functions that make up the Framework Core.

Figure 15: Steps for the ALLEGRO risk assessment process.

2.4. CRAMM. CRAMM (CCTA Risk Analysis and Management Method) [42] is a qualitative risk analysis and management tool developed by the UK government's Central Computer and Telecommunications Agency. It has been the UK government's preferred risk analysis method for years, but the project seems to receive no updates since 2003. It comprises three stages, each supported by objective questionnaires and guidelines. The first two stages identify and analyze the risks to the system. The third stage recommends how these risks should be managed. Specifically, the three steps are:

- 1) The establishment of the objectives for security by:
- 2) Defining the boundary for the study for Risk Assess-

Figure 16: The steps of the CORAS method.

ment.

- 3) Identifying and valuing the physical assets that form part of the system.
- 4) Determining the value of the data held by interviewing users about the potential business impacts that could arise from unavailability, destruction, disclosure or modification.
- 5) Identifying and valuing the software assets that form part of the system.
- 6) The assessment of the risks to the proposed system and the requirements for security by:
- 7) Identifying and assessing the type and level of threats that may affect the system.
- 8) Assessing the extent of the system's vulnerabilities to the identified threats.
- 9) Combining threat and vulnerability assessments with asset values to calculate measures of risks.
- 10) Identification and selection of countermeasures that are commensurate with the measures of risks calculated in the previous step.

The method is supported by a tool called CRAMM tool.

2.5. CORAS. CORAS [23] is a framework for conducting cybersecurity risk analysis. It provides a customized language for cybersecurity threat and risk modeling and comes with detailed guidelines explaining how the language should be used to capture and model relevant information during the various stages of the security analysis. The CORAS method is divided into eight steps illustrated in Figure 16.

2.6. NIST SP 800-39. The NIST SP 800-39 [18]. It is a special publication on Information Security Risk Management which presents a comprehensive process composed of four main activities.

- 1) Frame risk (i.e., establish the context for risk-based decisions).
- 2) Assess risk.
- 3) Respond to risk once determined.

Figure 17: The activities steps of the in the NIST SP 800-39 risk management process

- 4) Monitor risk on an ongoing basis using effective organizational communications and a feedback loop for continuous improvement in the risk-related activities of organizations.

Each of the steps in the risk management process is described in a structured manner, focusing on inputs and preconditions activities/tasks, and outputs resulting from the step. Figure 16 illustrates the processes in risk management.

2.7. ENISA EBIOS (Expression des Besoins et Identification des Objectifs de Sécurité) Risk Manager.

ENISA EBIOS Risk Manager [6] is an information security risk management method, created under the French General Secretariat of National Defense, consistent with ISO 31000:2018 and ISO/IEC 27005, and enables the risk management requirements of ISO/IEC 27001 to be met. The main parts can be summarized in the following six steps:

- 1) Establish the context.
- 2) Assess targeted and sophisticated risks.
- 3) Deal with the identified risks in a proportionate manner.
- 4) Accept residual risks.
- 5) Communicate risks.
- 6) Monitor and review risks.

2.8. BSI IT-Grundschutz. BSI IT-Grundschutz [17] (standard BSI 200-3) has been developed by the Federal Office for Information Security in Germany. It, before starting the risk analysis, involves a basic security check to verify the security measures that have been implemented. Risk assessment identifies the threats which have not been avoided by the measures, such as residual threats.

These threats can be mitigated by additional security measures. BSI IT-Grundschutz adopts a qualitative risk analysis approach that is associated with a primitive computational technique for the analysis and correlation of the assessment information. The method is compliant with ISO/IEC 27001 as it addresses the defined requirements as

well as being suitable for the implementation of the ISMS process described in ISO/IEC 27002.

The goal of the IT-Grundschutz Risk Assessment methodology is to provide a qualitative method for identification, analysis and evaluation of security incidents that might be damaging to the business, that is also consistent and usable with the rest of the standard, and that can be applied efficiently. The standards describe a two-tier risk assessment: one is designed for reaching a “standard” level of security, while a second “supplementary risk analysis” can be undertaken by companies that desire an approach customized to their specific needs or sector or that have special security requirements.

For implementing a standard Information Security Management System based on BSI IT-Grundschutz, the Risk Assessment is done by using the BSI IT-Grundschutz Catalogs. These catalogs contain repositories of common threat scenarios and standard security countermeasures applicable to most IT environments and grouped by modules corresponding to various business environments and Information System components. In order to achieve a higher level of information security, a supplementary risk analysis based on BSI IT-Grundschutz can also be performed as follows:

- Prepare an overview of threats: a list of relevant threats is created for each asset that is to be analyzed by using the IT-Grundschutz catalog.
- Determine additional threats: Any threats special to the application scenario are identified via a brainstorming session.
- Assess the threats: The threat summary is systematically analyzed to determine if the implemented and/or planned security measures provide adequate protection for each target object and threat. Thus, all relevant security mechanisms are checked for completeness, strength and reliability.
- Select safeguards for handling risks: Decisions are made at management level on the way risks not adequately mitigated are to be handled. Options include: reducing risk via safeguards, avoiding risk, transferring risk and accepting risk.
- Consolidated results: The new security policy and mechanisms as a whole are verified, checked for consistency, user friendliness and adequacy to the target environment.

2.9. MEHARI. Méthode Harmonisée d’Analyse de Risques (MEHARI) [25] is a free of charge qualitative risk analysis and management method developed by CLUSIF (Club for the Security of Information in France/Club de la Sécurité de l’Information Français). MEHARI provides a consistent methodology, with appropriate knowledge bases such as manuals and guides that describe the different modules (stakes, risks, vulnerabilities) designed to assist people involved in security management (CISOs, risk managers, auditors, CIOs), in their various tasks and actions. The methodology is suitable for the implementation of the ISMS process described by ISO/IEC 27001.

MEHARI describes a complex process, including cyclic Risk Management steps as well as the creation of a customized knowledge base. MEHARI also provides guidelines for the cybersecurity risk assessment, as follows.

- Identification of a threat scenario (either using the knowledge base or by directly, manually, identifying possible malfunctions).
- Evaluation of natural exposure (“default” exposure from environment).
- Evaluation of dissuasive and preventive factors.
- Evaluation of protective, remediation and recuperative factors.
- Evaluation of potentiality (i.e., how likely the risk is).
- Evaluation of intrinsic impact (i.e., consequences) by filling in a table provided by the methodology in which the impact of a certain scenario on the CIA properties for different categories of assets will be reported.
- Evaluation of impact and impact reduction via automated computation.
- Global Risk evaluation taking into account the previous factors.
- The method supports quantitative, scenario-based analysis of risk, and the overall process is similar to the one described in the ISO/IEC 27005 standard.

2.10. MAGERIT. MAGERIT [8, 35] is an open methodology for risk analysis and management developed by the Spanish Higher Council for Electronic Government and offered as a framework and guide to the public administration. It is the answer to the increasing dependency of public and private organizations on information technologies to fulfill their mission and reach their business objectives.

MAGERIT users undertake the responsibility of running the risk analysis process via workshops and interviews, with specific representatives of the organization participating only in specific phases of the assessment process. It is compliant with ISO/IEC 27005, covers all the requirements defined by the ISO/IEC 27001, and conforms with the code of implementation of an ISMS specified by ISO/IEC 27002:2005.

The Risk Analysis process consists of:

- Determine the relevant assets for the organization, their inter-relationships and their value.
- Determine the threats to which those assets are exposed.
- Determine what safeguards are available and how effective they are against the risk.
- Estimate the impact, defined as the damage to the asset arising from the appearance of the threat.
- Estimate the risk, defined as the weighted impact on the rate of occurrence.

2.11. ISRAM. Information Security Risk Analysis Method (ISRAM) [21] was developed in December 2003 at the National Research Institute of Electronics and Cryptology and the Gebze Institute of Technology in Turkey. It is a quantitative approach to risk analysis where a survey-based model is used to analyze risk in information security. The

method defines two main attributes of risks, i.e., probability and consequence of a security breach, to conduct two separate and independent surveys.

The risk factor is a numerical value corresponding to a qualitative, high, medium or low value, on which risk management decisions are based. ISRAM is designed for analyzing the risks of complex information systems and consists of seven steps. The first four steps are the preparation phase where the surveys are constructed. During step 5 the surveys are completed and risk analysis is performed during step 6. The final step is the assessment of the result. ISRAM is compliant with ISO/IEC 27002 and provides support of the ISO/IEC 27001 ISMS standard. It is also supported by a freeware tool.

2.12. FAIR. Factor Analysis of Information Risk (FAIR) [40] is a taxonomy of the factors that contribute to risk and how they affect each other. It is primarily concerned with establishing accurate probabilities for the frequency and magnitude of data loss events. The FAIR methodology addresses the issue of information security being practiced “as an art rather than a science”. As such, its goal is to rely less on the practitioner’s experience, intuition, or best practices; instead, FAIR derives outputs from repeatable, consistent, financially sound computations.

FAIR underlines that risk is an uncertain event and one should not focus on what is possible, but on how probable a given event is. This probabilistic approach is applied to every factor that is analyzed and the risk is the probability of a loss tied to an asset defined as the “probable frequency and probable magnitude of future loss.” FAIR further decomposes risk into probable frequency and probable loss so that risk can be quantitatively measured. The FAIR Basic Risk Assessment Guide describes a process comprised of ten steps, spread across four stages:

- 1) Identify scenario components.
- 2) Evaluate loss event frequency.
- 3) Evaluate probable loss magnitude.
- 4) Derive and articulate risk.

The FAIR methodology is complementary to most other Risk Management methodologies and can be used in conjunction with NIST 800-30 [9], ISO/IEC 27002, or COBIT.

2.13. PRISM. The prioritize-resource-implement-standardize-monitor (PRISM) [11] framework proposes a process-oriented methodology that requires organizations to undertake the five-step approach suggested by its name. The framework originates from the fundamental theory that the lack of strategic focus on prioritization of cyber activities is a key gap in the tailoring of a successful risk management process. Prioritizing includes identifying the main risk drivers and interdependencies among them. The remaining steps ensure resourcing and implementation of identified and necessary security controls are integrated into the organization’s enterprise systems and processes. Moreover, the framework recognizes the constrained resource environment and thereby enables optimal decision-making at the CIO level working within

the constraints. PRISM is a qualitative model to structure the decision framework as a first step in the cyber risk management process. While quantitative models lead to a detailed assessment, a decision framework using a qualitative model helps to start the planning process in a way that provides value to executives.

3. Proofs

Here is a list of additional mathematical proofs.

3.1. Entropy of OTP. Here we give the proof that the entropy of OTP (One-Time Pad), implemented as XOR, is exactly the entropy of its key. As a consequence, if the message we wish to encrypt is longer than the key then OTP is no longer a perfect encryption algorithm.

Let $\mathbb{B} := \{0, 1\}$ be our alphabet (i.e. bits). Let $m \in \mathbb{B}^n$ be the message we wish to encrypt of length $n \geq 0$ and $k = k_1 \dots k_l \in \mathbb{B}^l$ be the key of length $l \geq 0$.

Suppose that the message is longer than the key, so $n > l$. This means there exists nonnegative integers p, q such that $n = lp + q$. So to calculate the XOR between the message and the key we have to concatenate the key to itself p times and then concatenate the first q symbols of k . Denoting the bit-wise XOR with \oplus we have:

$$OTP(m, k) = m \oplus \tilde{k}$$

Where:

$$\tilde{k} := \overbrace{(k \dots k)}^{p\text{-times}} k_1 \dots k_q$$

Let H be Shannon's entropy and p the probability, then the entropy with respect to the key is:

$$H(OTP(m, k)) = - \sum_{\substack{o:=OTP(m,k) \\ k \in \mathbb{B}^l}} p(o) \log(p(o))$$

Noting that OTP is injective, we can calculate the probability as:

$$\begin{aligned} p(o) &= \frac{|\{k \mid OTP(m, k) = o \text{ for } k \in \mathbb{B}^l\}|}{|\mathbb{B}^l|} \\ &= \frac{1}{2^l} \end{aligned}$$

So we obtain:

$$\begin{aligned} H(OTP(m, k)) &= - \sum_{\substack{o:=OTP(m,k) \\ k \in \mathbb{B}^l}} \frac{1}{2^l} \log\left(\frac{1}{2^l}\right) \\ &= 2^l \frac{1}{2^l} \log(2^l) \\ &= \log(2^l) \\ &= l \end{aligned}$$

So the entropy is exactly l , which is exactly the entropy of the key, if we assume that the key is generated in a

truly random manner, so with a uniform distribution over the space of all keys of length l (i.e. with probability $\log(\frac{1}{2^l})$).

This proves that the entropy of OTP is limited by the length of the key, in particular if the message is longer than the key, then we lose the optimality of OTP.